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Professional Self-Conception In Adolescents**A.O. Nurjonov***Researcher at Mamun University***<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18013148>**

In modern psychology, there is no single, clear definition of the concept of “self-determination” in the process of choosing a profession, and this concept is used in a manner closely related to the concepts of “formation” and “development”.

The main driving force of professional self-determination is the individual's identification with social groups and institutions, his desire to integrate into the social context. In different cultural, historical and biographical conditions, this desire can be general to different areas of labor and directed to different levels of qualification, depending on the volume and quality of professional education.

According to the differential diagnostic approach, F. Parsonson, G. Munsterberg, G. Bogen, each person is optimally suited to only one profession, primarily in terms of his individual qualities, and his professionally significant abilities. The level of professional success and satisfaction with the profession depends on the degree of correspondence between the individual qualities of a person and the requirements of the profession, and professional choice is essentially a conscious and rational process. In this case, the person himself or a career counselor can determine his individual predisposition to psychological or physical qualities and compare them with the requirements of different professions [5]. It is emphasized that personal qualities play an important role in professional success and satisfaction with the profession [4]. In our opinion, the basis of professional success in adolescents can be associated with achieving success in their activities, professional growth and achieving their goals. Their satisfaction with their profession is a positive mental state that arises as a result of the correspondence of their chosen profession to their interests, values, and needs. Both are directly related not only to knowledge and skills, but also to the system of personal qualities. Conscious development of personal qualities in adolescence, correct assessment of one's interests and abilities ensures future professional success and satisfaction with the profession. It can be said that the development of personal qualities in adolescents is the most important basis for professional achievements [2].

The professional formation of a person is studied in detail in the works of T.V. Kudryavtsev, E.A. Klimov, E.F. Zeer, V.A. Bodrov, Yu.P. Povarenkov and others, and the person as the object of development is in the main place and he is the main factor of progressive changes in the human psyche. The social situation of development and leading activity are taken as the criteria for the periodization of professional self-

determination. The process of professional formation begins with the formation of professional intentions and covers the period from the moment of their formation to the moment of their withdrawal from professional life [1]. It can be said that the period of formation of professional intentions falls on adolescence, when a person begins to understand his interests and abilities. He collects information about professions, and a professional model is formed based on dreams and ideals. This period serves as the foundation for choosing a professional direction. In fact, the stage of choosing a profession and preparing for it begins in adolescence and continues until adulthood and is carried out in the process of studying, acquiring special knowledge and skills, and practicing. In general, a person adapts himself to the chosen profession.

The process of professionalization is described by S. Glukhanyuk, N.V. Kuzmina, A.R. Fonarev, N.N. Nechayev, L.M. Mitinas studied and considered the subject of activity as an object of development, in some cases interpreted as a specialist, in others as a professional employee. Accordingly, four stages of professionalization are distinguished depending on the level of successful performance of the activity: professional adaptation (profadaptation), primary professionalization, secondary professionalization and the stage of mastery [3]. Thus, during adolescence, a person begins to think about choosing a profession, dreams and intentions are formed. Although he has not yet fully entered the professional environment, he imagines himself in different professions. This period is a period of “testing himself” for a teenager, preparing for future adaptation through various activities, interest in subjects, and identification of abilities. By the end of adolescence, a person knows more clearly which field he is interested in.

Obtaining knowledge in the chosen field (lyceum, college, training courses) is considered the initial stage of acquiring qualifications. Personal qualities in adolescents - responsibility, discipline, determination - also develop, which become the basis for the formation of professional skills. During this period, the psychological foundation for the level of professional maturity in adolescents is created. Their own “I-concept” is formed, and they begin to look for an answer to the question “Who am I?” Motivation, interest and diligence formed during adolescence can later lead to professional maturity [5].

So, based on the above, the process of self-realization is considered one of the important criteria when making a professional choice during adolescence, and it is important to take into account such aspects.

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